

Optimal reconstruction of upper limb kinematics and muscular activation through multi-modal under-sensorized wearable systems

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Abstract—Wearable sensing systems are a promising solution for unobtrusive monitoring of the human musculoskeletal state. However, consideration regarding cost and wearability could limit the number of sensors used to retrieve data. We previously developed a theoretical approach for reconstructing both the upper limb kinematic and muscular states, employing only a restricted quantity of optimal sensory information. However, no attempt has yet been attempted to implement this technology to develop a physical under-sensorized wearable device. In this work, we present the design of an under-sensorized wearable system focusing on minimising the number of sensor units used. The system exploits data gathered from Inertial Measurement Units (IMUs) and surface Electromyography (sEMG) electrodes to estimate the entire upper limb biomechanical state. Relying on two IMUs only and eight sEMG sensors, the system proposed in this paper can reconstruct all 17 Degrees of Freedom (5 joints and 12 muscles) of the human arm with a median normalized RMS error of 8.5% on the non-measured joints and 2.5% on the non-measured muscles.

Index Terms—Sensor Fusion, IMUs, sEMG, upper limb

I. INTRODUCTION

Assessing the musculoskeletal condition of the human body plays a vital role in various fields, including rehabilitation and assistive technologies [1], monitoring athletes [2], and facilitating human-robot interaction and collaboration [3].

The complexity of the considered system requires a large number of heterogeneous sensing elements, such as surface electromyography (sEMG) for muscle activity and inertial measurement unit (IMU) for the kinematic assessment [4]. However, wearable solutions generally discourage the placement of numerous body-mounted sensors, as this could adversely affect the device’s form factor and overall wearability [5].

One potential method to address this problem is by leveraging the covariation patterns among Degrees of Freedom (DoFs) within our body, commonly referred to as *motor synergies* [6]. This paradigm can be exploited to provide insights for developing minimal sensing setups for human motion.

An interesting framework is the one proposed in [7], where Minimum Variance Estimation (MVE) was used in combination with the functional Principal Component Analysis (fPCA) to estimate multi-modal time-varying data of the upper limb. However, this work assumes that any joint can

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Fig. 1. Schematic structure of the estimation procedure (from [8]). The framework is divided into 3 different phases: first (*Encoding phase*) temporal fPC decomposition maps signals into the weight vector; after that, *Minimum Variance Estimation (MVE)* combines the encoded measurements with *a priori* information to estimate for the missing components of measures; finally, fPCs are used to convert back the weight vector of estimation to the temporal domain (*Decoding phase*).

be measured independently, without any non-linear mapping between state variables and sensors being considered.

In this work, building on the theoretical framework proposed in [7], we present the design of an under-sensorized wearable system for multimodal recording of the biomechanical state of the human upper limb. The optimal sensing setup founded in [7] was generalized to the more compelling scenario of data collection from a set of IMUs and sEMGs. In this situation, the goal shifts from choosing individual degrees of freedom associated with reduced estimation uncertainty to reducing the number of sensor elements in use. Our new optimal joint angles now strike a balance between reconstructing with the lowest error and minimizing the employed sensing resources. We implemented this design in a real prototype composed of the optimal set of sEMGs identified in [7] and only two IMUs to measure shoulder joints using an Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF). To test the framework we have collected a large number of movements to prove the effectiveness of the estimation reaching a median normalized RMS error of 8.5% on the non-measured joints and of 2.5% on the non-measured EMGs.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Our work is based on the combination of MVE and fPCA to estimate missing temporal signals. For the sake of space, in this paper, we give only a quick overview of the framework, while for more detailed information we refer the interested reader to [8].

The MVE approach enables to exploit a dataset of recorded movement as *a priori* information to complete for missing measurements. A system with a linear relation between the state x and the measurements z is defined as $z = Hx + v$, where H is a full row rank measurement matrix and v is the measurement noise. If the dimension of the state vector is higher than the output vector’s one, there are infinite

solutions for a given measurement. MVE is able to exploit the covariation patterns between the elements of the state vector contained in a previously recorded dataset. This *a priori* information is organized in a covariance matrix P_0 defined as:

$$P_0 = \frac{(X - \bar{x})(X - \bar{x})^T}{N - 1}, \quad (1)$$

where \bar{x} is a matrix whose columns contain the average μ_0 of X . Considering a Gaussian noise v with zero mean and covariance matrix R , it is possible to compute the best estimate \hat{x} of x in closed form as:

$$\hat{x} = (H^T R^{-1} H + P_0^{-1})^{-1} (H^T R^{-1} y + P_0^{-1} \mu_0). \quad (2)$$

However, MVE is not able to handle temporal signals and it is necessary to encode the data in a static domain to enable a reliable estimation of P_0 . To solve this problem, we use an estimation framework divided into 3 different phases: i) the encoding phase, where the measured signals are translated from the time domain to a static domain; ii) the estimation phase, where MVE is used to estimate the elements of the state vector related to the lacking measurements; and iii) the decoding phase, where the estimated state vector is translated back in the time domain to re-obtain the temporal muscles activation. A graphical representation of this approach is depicted in Fig. 1.

To perform encoding and decoding phases, we used fPCA, a functional extension of Principal Component Analysis. In a nutshell, fPCA builds a basis of function from a dataset of time-varying data. All the elements of this basis are ordered with respect to the amount of variance explained by each of them (the first component explains the higher amount of variance of the original dataset). Considering a signal $z(t)$, its linear functional decomposition can be defined as:

$$z(t) \simeq \bar{z} + S_0(t) + \sum_{i=1}^{S_{max}} \alpha_i S_i(t), \quad (3)$$

where \bar{z} is the average value, $S_0(t)$ is the average time signal of the entire dataset, $S_i(t)$ is the i^{th} functional Principal Component (fPC) and α_i is the weight related to the component $S_i(t)$. More details on theoretical and practical aspects of fPCA can be found in [9]. With this approach, it is possible to translate a set of M time series easily in a static vector made by fPCs weights defined as:

$$x = [\bar{z}_1 \ \alpha_{1,1} \ \dots \ \alpha_{1,k} \ | \ \dots \ | \ \bar{z}_M \ \alpha_{M,1} \ \dots \ \alpha_{M,k}]^T. \quad (4)$$

III. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

We used the results obtained in [7] to build the sensing system. The muscle activation profiles during motion were acquired through the Delsys Bagnoli EMG System ($f_{sampling} = 2400$ Hz). The recorded signal was filtered with the following 3-step procedure: 1) a 1st-order low-pass Butterworth filter ($f_{cutoff} = 500$ Hz) to decrease the high-frequency noise; 2) a 1st-order high-pass Butterworth filter ($f_{cutoff} = 20$ Hz) to get rid of the persistent and slow-changing components; 3) rectification; and 4) a 1st-order low-pass Butterworth filter ($f_{cutoff} = 1$ Hz) for the signal envelope extraction. Kinematic data were collected using LSM9DS1 inertial sensors built in Arduino Nano 33 BLE boards and serially transmitted to a computer at a $f_{sample} = 120$ Hz. A calibration phase was performed to estimate how the sensor was mounted on the arm. The information gathered by the IMUs was given to an Unscented Kalman Filter

(UKF) to obtain an estimation of the shoulder joint angles. To validate the kinematic estimation, we used the Xsens MTw Awinda wearable system as ground truth. We recorded the kinematic data through Xsens proprietary software at the fastest $f_{sample} = 60$ Hz. We performed Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) [10] to synchronize the Xsens data with EMG and IMU signals.

We used as benchmark for our framework the movement proposed in the SoftPro protocol (30 different tasks of daily living) [11]. To record data, 9 able-bodied subjects (6 male and 3 female, age 28.2 ± 2.7 , all right-handed) were asked to execute different task, each performed three times, for a total of 90 movements per subject. They agreed to participate after being fully informed. The experiments were granted permission by the Committee on Bioethics of the University of Pisa (Review No. 30/2020) in conformity with the Declaration of Helsinki.

To evaluate the system, we computed the Normalized Root Mean Square Error (NRMSE) between the estimated DoFs and the relative ground truth. We have obtained a median NRMSE for the estimated joints of 8.5%, while for muscle activation our framework achieved a maximum median NRMSE just above 4%.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we presented a possible approach to design under-sensorized wearable system to evaluate the biomechanical state of the human body. We briefly showed the most noticeable results, referring the interested reader to [8]. The proposed system could be a first step in the design of whole-body multi-modal sensing, where the number of sensing elements to get an estimation of the entire biomechanical state of the human body could lead to ergonomics and economic problems and the reduction of the dimensionality of the wearable system become crucial for the spreading of this type of technologies.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. Bai, M. G. Pepper, Y. Yan, M. Phillips, and M. Sakel, "Low cost inertial sensors for the motion tracking and orientation estimation of human upper limbs in neurological rehabilitation," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 54 254–54 268, 2020.
- [2] M. T. Worsey, H. G. Espinosa, J. B. Shepherd, and D. V. Thiel, "Inertial sensors for performance analysis in combat sports: A systematic review," *Sports*, vol. 7, no. 1, p. 28, 2019.
- [3] P. A. Lasota, T. Fong, J. A. Shah *et al.*, "A survey of methods for safe human-robot interaction," *Foundations and Trends® in Robotics*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 261–349, 2017.
- [4] A. Filippeschi, N. Schmitz, M. Miezal, G. Bleser, E. Ruffaldi, and D. Stricker, "Survey of motion tracking methods based on inertial sensors: A focus on upper limb human motion," *Sensors*, vol. 17, no. 6, p. 1257, 2017.
- [5] C. Pacchierotti, S. Sinclair, M. Solazzi, A. Frisoli, V. Hayward, and D. Prattichizzo, "Wearable haptic systems for the fingertip and the hand: taxonomy, review, and perspectives," *IEEE transactions on haptics*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 580–600, 2017.
- [6] M. L. Latash, "One more time about motor (and non-motor) synergies," *Experimental Brain Research*, vol. 239, no. 10, pp. 2951–2967, 2021.
- [7] G. Averta, M. Iuculano, P. Salaris, and M. Bianchi, "Optimal reconstruction of human motion from scarce multimodal data," *IEEE Transactions on Human-Machine Systems*, 2022.
- [8] P. Bonifati, M. Baracca, M. Menolotto, G. Averta, and M. Bianchi, "A multi-modal under-sensorized wearable system for optimal kinematic and muscular tracking of human upper limb motion," *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 7, p. 3716, 2023.
- [9] J. O. Ramsay, *Functional data analysis*. Wiley Online Library, 2006.
- [10] M. Müller, "Dynamic time warping," *Information retrieval for music and motion*, pp. 69–84, 2007.
- [11] G. Averta, F. Barontini, V. Catrambone, S. Haddadin, G. Handjaras, J. P. Held, T. Hu, E. Jakobowitz, C. M. Kanzler, J. Kühn *et al.*, "U-limb: A multi-modal, multi-center database on arm motion control in healthy and post-stroke conditions," *GigaScience*, vol. 10, no. 6, p. giab043, 2021.